

ISic2952

I.Sicily inscription 2952

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2014.12.14 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance

Viale Principe Umberto

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù, Museo Mandralisca, inventory 120

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108677

1. Δέκομε Λαί

2. λει Μέγα

3. χάρε

Edition: PHI331407

1. Δέκομε Λαί-

2. λει Μέγα,

3. χάρε.

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284917

EDR 108677
EDCS 64400392
PHI 331407

Bibliography

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